

E PLURIBUS UNUM: THE AMERICAN CULTURE OF MONOLINGUALISM

by

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DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.6654273

A Project Submitted in Partial Fulfillment of the
Requirements to Graduate with University Honors

The University Honors Program
California State University, Fullerton

May 2022

Approved by:

Date:

12 May 2022

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5/31/2022

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ABSTRACT

There are few concepts more integral to the American identity than the “melting pot.” From a linguistic standpoint, this is appreciably and quantifiably true. In fact, Americans speak over 350 languages at home on a daily basis. Nonetheless, multilingualism has rarely been encouraged throughout the history of the United States, and this social and political attitude has caused the U.S. to lag behind its developed peers in both language education and language retention. This project is a multifaceted examination of this issue that operates under one unifying concept: synthesis. Across academic literature, there has been extensive research about the history of bilingual education and attitudes toward bilingualism from a social perspective. Likewise, there is extensive journalism and criticism regarding current public policy toward language education. Unfortunately, these issues are always evaluated separately, overlooking the inextricable nature of these phenomena in a way that is detrimental to the broad quality of research in this field. This project aims to be the first among to unite historical, social, political, governmental and educational inquiries of the challenge of sustaining multilingualism in the United States. After a detailed analysis in each of these areas, it also discusses potential reforms to remedy America’s language problem.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

An enormous number of people were necessary to make this project possible. More than anything, however, I want to thank every person who has ever believed in my ability to learn Spanish. The opportunity to fall in love with a second language has been one of the defining experiences of my life, and I could not have done it if several people did not loyally reinforce my confidence when I started to doubt myself. I am grateful to my high school Spanish teacher, **Señor Celano**, who made Spanish an easy language to love. I am also grateful for **Dr. Eric Carbajal**, who encouraged me not to drop out of my college Spanish class on the very first day. I am grateful for **Dr. Reyes Fidalgo**, who saw me as a student that could not only get by in Spanish, but thrive. Last, and most of all, I am grateful for *mi cuate* and partner in Spanish **Rebeca De La Cruz**, without whom I could not have completed these last four years in the Spanish major.

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INTRODUCTION: OUT OF MANY, ONE

As one of the most diverse countries in human history, foreign languages are ubiquitous in the United States. In fact, the term “foreign” may be misapplied, as the 350 languages spoken nationwide are not some imported commodity, but rather an integral part of the daily life of millions of Americans who were born and raised in the United States¹. Since its inception, this country has made the unification of eclectic groups part of its core identity. It was no accident that in 1776, when the United States was only a Declaration of Independence and a Continental Army, the Latin phrase “*E pluribus unum*” was selected as the fledgling country’s motto: out of many, one². With the choice to emphasize any aspect of the collection of colonies struggling against the mighty British Empire, the founders chose to emphasize diversity³.

Unfortunately, the glorified American goal of unifying a diverse populace inevitably wields an assimilatory effect against each individual culture involved. The American National Standards Institute notes that standardized currency, for example, requires some degree of nationalism to be successful because the benefits of standardization are only enjoyed when other currencies are driven out of the market⁴. Language works in the same way. For decades, organizations like U.S. English have fought for the exclusivity of English in the United States at the expense of other languages as a means of this very unification: “in a pluralistic nation such as ours, government should foster the similarities that unite us, rather than the differences that

¹“Census Bureau Reports at Least 350 Languages Spoken in U.S. Homes.” U.S. Census Bureau, 8 Oct. 2021, <https://www.census.gov/newsroom/archives/2015-pr/cb15-185.html>.

² García Gorrido, Isabel and Miguel Fernández Álvarez. “Historical Perspectives of Bilingual Education in the United States.” *Teoría de la Educación- Educación y Cultura en la Sociedad de la Información*, vol. 12, no. 3, 2011, pp. 41-55.

³ García Gorrido and Álvarez 43

⁴Kelechava, Brad. “Standardization of Money.” *American National Standards Institute*, 17 Aug. 2016, <https://blog.ansi.org/2016/08/standardization-of-money/#gref>.

separate us.”⁵ In the modern United States, the rallying cry of the greatest enemy of multilingualism has become the same as the rationale of those that support multilingualism: supporting diversity.

For this reason, linguistic diversity continues to face its fair share of discrimination. When one thinks of the people who further that discrimination, they most likely think of individuals who display racial bias in the explicit and traditional sense. Perhaps John Tanton, a co-founder of the U.S. English organization, is the best embodiment of this expectation. As an influential voice on immigration issues for the better part of the twentieth century, Tanton is famous for establishing the Federation for American Immigration Reform (FAIR) and the Center for Immigration Studies (CIS), all of which advocate a conservative stance on immigration issues.⁶ Scholars such as Woods et. al have identified Tanton’s alarming involvement with white nationalist and eugenics organizations as well as his advocacy that the U.S. should deny entry specifically to Latin American immigrants for a variety of racially-motivated reasons.⁷ Tanton is the stereotype for a national voice who would fight efforts toward expanded multilingualism.

And yet, Tanton is not multilingualism’s great threat. Monolingualist efforts persist in the United States not because of support from disreputable figures like Tanton, but because of steady backing from credible figures. To anyone who studies language, the list of America’s most prominent supporters of “English only” is truly surprising: Founding Father Benjamin Franklin, President and Mount Rushmore icon Teddy Roosevelt, a Canadian-born senator from California

⁵ Lewelling, Vickie. “Official English and English Plus: An Update.” *ERIC Clearinghouse on Languages and Linguistics*, 1997, pp. 2.

⁶ “John Tanton.” *Southern Poverty Law Center*, <https://www.splcenter.org/fighting-hate/extremist-files/individual/john-tanton>.

⁷ Woods et. al. “The Impression Management Tactics of an Immigration Think Tank.” *Sociological Focus*, vol. 48, issue 4, 2015, pp. 354-372.

with Japanese ancestry, a Chilean-American CEO, and more⁸. This group of four carries a lethal formula. Each of these individuals was fluent in three languages or more, carried great credibility in the eye of the public, and believed that the best treatment for linguistic diversity in the United States was to make English the only acceptable form of communication.

Of course, the credibility of advocates of monolingualism is just one of a variety of complex explanations for the cause, but the phenomenon itself is clear: monolingualism prospers in the American melting pot. Census estimates indicate that approximately 21 percent of the U.S. population speaks a language other than English at home, but only an estimated 20 percent of Americans are bilingual.⁹ These nearly identical numbers would not be possible if not for the linguistic fact that separates the United States from all other developed (and many developing) nations: almost no Americans are bilingual without familial ties to a foreign region. In 2008, a national survey of American high schools revealed that almost all (93 percent) offered foreign language classes¹⁰. Even so, less than one percent of U.S. adults report proficiency in a language they learned at school¹¹. At the collegiate level, only 7 percent of students are enrolled in language courses, a number that does not inspire confidence to raise America's low rates of foreign language education¹².

Beyond statistics, monolingualism has a significant cultural grip on the United States as well. Jennifer Leeman, a professor of Spanish at George Mason University, has argued that the United States revolves around a "monoglossic culture," one that views English not just as the

⁸ Pavlenko, Aneta. "We have room for but one language here: Language and national identity in the U.S. at the turn of the 20th century." *Multilingua*, pp. 163-196.

⁹Matthews, Jay. "Half of the world is bilingual. What's our problem?" *The Washington Post*, 25 Apr. 2019, https://www.washingtonpost.com/local/education/half-the-world-is-bilingual-whats-our-problem/2019/04/24/1c2b0cc2-6625-11e9-a1b6-b29b90efa879_story.html

¹⁰ Friedman.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² *Ibid.*

American language but as “a key marker to personhood and national belonging¹³.” If English is a prerequisite to personhood, then other languages are at risk for being treated as a disease or threat. Leeman describes exactly this phenomenon, arguing that English has reached such an invulnerable status in American culture that assistance for those who do not speak English is similar to assistance with disabilities. In one Oregon case, attorney arguments centered around the idea that the inability to speak English constituted a handicap for the defendant: “a person who doesn’t speak English and cannot communicate in English is defined in [state law] as a handicapped person, and an interpreter shall be appointed to assist that individual.¹⁴” This view of minority languages as disabilities indicates that languages are not only sparsely learned across the United States, but sparsely respected.

At a social, political, and governmental level, the United States has faithfully adhered to the doctrine of *E Pluribus Unum*. Out of many languages, only one is allowed to thrive. This paper critically examines why the unrivaled status of English in the United States has come at the expense of other languages. First, it analyzes American monolingualism from a historical perspective, documenting the evolution of attitudes toward languages other than English as well as the nation’s approaches to foreign language education. Next, it turns to an expansive, modern outlook by evaluating current policies to understand their impact on the language landscape. Finally, it considers whether the monolingual condition must be permanent in the United States. To answer this question, it examines language education tactics from developed nations with far more success in linguistic education and retention and briefly discusses prominent theories surrounding proposals for reform. Although other scholars have outlined the history of

¹³Leeman, Jennifer. “It’s all about English: the interplay of monolingual ideologies, language policies and the U.S. Census Bureau’s statistics on multilingualism.” *De Gruyter Mouton*, 2018, pp. 23.

¹⁴ Leeman 32

language attitudes in the United States, this paper aims to view the history and current policy landscape as complementary tools for constructing effective language reform.

PART I: HISTORY

“These workers don’t suffer, they don’t even speak English.”

- American railroad executive before Congress, 1904

A. Linguistic Attitudes from the Founding Fathers to the 21st Century

Two decades before the start of the American Revolutionary War, the American war over multilingualism was already in full swing. In 1750, Benjamin Franklin sought to make English the official (and exclusive) language of the American colonies¹. In personal writings, he made it clear that his preference for English was largely grounded in a fear of replacement by other languages and, more broadly, a fear of replacement by German immigrants: “Why should Pennsylvania, founded by the English, become a Colony of Aliens, who will shortly be so numerous as to Germanize us instead of our Anglifying them, and will never adopt our Language or Customs, any more than they can acquire our Complexion².” Never a man of solely words, Franklin made key strides to reduce the influence of German through the schools he founded across Pennsylvania that allowed only English and had no issue “eliminat[ing] the use of any other languages.³” Historical evidence has made clear that the distaste that Franklin and his contemporaries had for the German language followed the typical pattern for language discrimination in that it was rooted in broader anti-German sentiment. In the 18th century, German immigrants were seen as lazy, illiterate, and dangerously Catholic⁴. Ironically, German

¹ García Gorrido and Álvarez 42.

² Baron, Dennis. “The Legendary English-Only Vote of 1795.” *Illinois University*, <http://faculty.las.illinois.edu/debaron/essays/legend.htm>.

³García Gorrido and Álvarez 45.

⁴ Baron.

immigrants in the 18th century were adopting English at an impressively high rate without this discriminatory pressure and, in many cases, removing their native language from their daily lives⁵. Through this, it is evident that foreign language resistance has long been rooted in a more general fear and animus toward immigrants as a whole-- before, even, this fear was compounded by racial strife.

As the United States found its footing and the 18th century drew to a close, language resistance persisted. In 1795, the Third U.S. Congress considered the contentious issue of whether federal laws should be available in German as well as English.⁶ This debate offered the first documented defense of multilinguistic attitudes in the young nation-- a somewhat begrudging argument from Representative Thomas Hartley of Pennsylvania-- that maintained laws would be more effective if they were more broadly understood⁷. Nonetheless, Congress rejected the legislation with little hesitation and President Washington approved that federal laws be published in English only⁸.

Although these early disputes over foreign languages can be characterized as formative, it would be a mistake to dramatize them into memorable moments. In reality, American dislike of foreign languages remained largely latent during the first century of the United States. The Articles of Confederation were published in both English and German⁹. Quietly, multilingualism was gaining a meaningful foothold in American society. Non-English ethnic groups grew throughout the United States and bilingual schools (teaching primarily German and English)

⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ García, Ofelia. "Bilingualism in the United States: Present Attitudes in the Light of Past Policies." pp. 147-158 <https://ofeliagarciaidotorg.files.wordpress.com/2011/02/bilingualism-in-the-us-present-attitudes-past-policies.pdf>.

operated in major cities such as Baltimore, St. Louis, Cleveland, and Cincinnati¹⁰. In fact, Ohio became a leader in multilingual policy by being the first state to formally authorize instruction in German and English in 1839.¹¹ Many other states soon followed Ohio's example, including the newly acquired territory of New Mexico in 1850, which became the first to authorize Spanish-English education.¹²

Multilingualism was far from supported in the United States, but it was not yet facing active opposition. Particularly before the 1880s, one could find communities across the growing nation that were dominated by Italian, Dutch, Polish, French, Czech, or German immigrants¹³. Because of their significant populations, these non-English ethnic communities enjoyed a modest amount of power that permitted them to introduce foreign languages as a course of instruction in American schools and, on occasion, as the medium of instruction itself.¹⁴ Regrettably, it bears noting that the relative freedom toward European immigrants was not also extended to their nonwhite counterparts. Precursors of English-only sentiment were present prior to 1880 in legislative discrimination against Native American and traditional African languages¹⁵. In fact, the Indian Peace Commission of 1868 had the specific goal of forcing Native American children to learn English, something that ushered many native languages toward extinction¹⁶. Nevertheless, in these early decades of the United States, the country still began to characterize itself as a truly multicultural and linguistically diverse nation.

¹⁰ Crawford, James. "Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era." *Education Week*, 1 April 1987, <https://www.edweek.org/teaching-learning/bilingual-education-traces-its-u-s-roots-to-the-colonial-era/1987/04>.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ García, O 148.

¹⁶ García Gorrido and Álvarez 45.

Unfortunately, this peaceful period of linguistic salutary neglect was decisively eradicated by the resurgence of nativism in the 1880s.¹⁷ Interestingly, it was not the rate of immigration that caused this dramatic shift, but the origin of these immigrants. Between 1880 and 1923, the United States tallied more than 35 million immigrants, the majority of whom were from southern and eastern Europe¹⁸. Americans were not so welcoming to this group as they were to their northern European neighbors of the preceding decades, viewing them as “inherently different from the existing white population” in a way that dangerously altered “the racial composition of the nation¹⁹.” As nativist groups like the Know Nothing Party rose to prominence, it was only a matter of time before this anti-immigrant sentiment was institutionalized and, eventually, codified.

Legislatively, this period saw the landmark separation of ethnoracial background and color-defined race, two categories that had before been treated as indistinguishable²⁰. In the late 19th century, the Census Bureau began inquiring about “mother tongue” as a less direct means of determining respondents’ ethnic background²¹. Thus, it was the differences in language between Americans that added nuance to the once hyper-simplistic government separation of “White” and “Black” (a color-defined race approach) by dividing the “White” category into a variety of different ethnicities²². Though somewhat progressive in the broader picture of language evolution in the United States, this Census was used for discriminatory purposes. By the time immigration became a contentious topic at end of the 19th century, lawmakers used this “mother tongue” Census data to indicate that the new “types” of immigrants (that is, immigrants not from northern

¹⁷ Crawford, “Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era.”

¹⁸ García, O 148.

¹⁹ Leeman 25.

²⁰ Leeman 25.

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² *Ibid.*

Europe) learned English more slowly and consequently were failing to assimilate²³. The manipulation of language statistics and attitudes became an extremely effective tool to harden nativist ideas into law. Before 1890, the United States passed four laws at the federal level with substantial limitations on immigration: the Chinese Exclusion Act of 1882, the Immigration Act of 1882, and two versions of the Alien Contract Labor Laws in 1885 and 1887²⁴.

Part of this wave of nativist legislation included the use of linguistic restrictions as a means of preventing immigrants from receiving education and becoming more economically competitive in the U.S. job market²⁵. These restrictions, founded on language, successfully plunged millions of new U.S. immigrants into a season of great economic hardship, fueling a poverty along lines of ethnicity that only served to worsen nativist stereotypes²⁶. As the 20th century began, important American leaders were already explicitly promoting English-only policies. The much-beloved President Theodore Roosevelt became an important voice on this issue by declaring that “We have room for but one language in this country and that is the English language, for we intend to see that the crucible turns our people out as Americans, of American nationality, and not as dwellers in a polyglot boarding house²⁷.” While he was governor of Iowa, future president Warren G. Harding wrote in the *New York Times* that languages other than English should never be used outside the home, and that religious observers who could not worship in English should not enjoy public religious services²⁸. The message at the turn of the century was clear: patriotic Americans trust only English.

²³ *Ibid.*

²⁴ “Early American Immigration Policies,” *U.S. Citizenship and Immigration Services*, <https://www.uscis.gov/about-us/our-history/overview-of-ins-history/early-american-immigration-policies#:~:text=Thus%2C%20as%20the%20number%20of,immigrating%20to%20the%20United%20States>.

²⁵ García, O 148.

²⁶ *Ibid.*

²⁷ García Gorrido and Álvarez 46.

²⁸ Baron.

Out of any group, it was the large population of German-American immigrants that experienced the most pronounced language discrimination. Even before World War I, speakers of German suffered attacks from the American Protective Association (APA), an anti-Catholic, anti-immigrant organization that openly sought to shut down the multilingual schools that had developed during the 19th century²⁹. Soon, native language abandonment became an inseparable part of the assimilation that was expected of all new immigrants: by 1906, all incoming male immigrants were required to pass a test of English fluency to enter the country³⁰. The 20th century expectation of linguistic assimilation as an element of becoming an American was considered by scholars to be nothing short of “devastating” to bilingual education of the era³¹.

Though these challenges reflect strongly negative attitudes before 1917, no event impacted foreign languages in America quite like World War I. The national distaste for German immigrants transformed into total distrust of an ethnic group that was now viewed as the enemy. In many states, it became outright illegal to speak German in public³². By 1923, a staggering 34 states had passed legislation mandating English as the only language for instruction in public schools³³. If foreign peoples were a threat, so too were their languages.

In the spirit of war, the governmental preference for new immigrants to learn English transformed into the expectation that these immigrants completely renounced the “ways” of their native country³⁴. A German, for example, who insisted on speaking their native language would continually be viewed with suspicion and could be treated with open contempt due to their perceived dual loyalty. Governor James Cox of Ohio called German “a distinctive menace to

²⁹ García Gorrido and Álvarez 45.

³⁰ *Ibid.*

³¹ *Ibid.*

³² Crawford, “Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era.”

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ Leeman 25

Americanism” and accused the German government of using it to sabotage the United States³⁵. Consequently, legislation hostile to language education grew bolder. In 1919, the state of Nebraska even passed a bill that flatly banned the teaching of all foreign languages³⁶. This law was just one result of a full-scale reactionary storm by nativist legislatures in the wake of the First World War, but a defiant Alaskan teacher by the name of Robert T. Meyer turned this law into the country’s first judicial battleground for multilingual education³⁷.

Meyer v. Nebraska (1923) proved to be such a formative case that most histories of American bilingualism mark the beginning of a new era precisely at the year 1923. After decades—arguably centuries—of uninterrupted attacks against foreign language education, multilingualism was dealt a substantial victory. The Supreme Court struck down the Nebraska law that prohibited the teaching of foreign languages under the Due Process Clause of the Fourteenth Amendment.³⁸ While dubbing it “desirable” for all residents of the United States to learn English, the Court’s decisive 7-2 majority argued that “a desirable end cannot be prompted by prohibited means.³⁹” In perhaps the nation’s darkest season for multilingualism, a light shone through, and from this moment forward there was at least minimal constitutional protection for foreign languages.

Despite its momentous timing, *Meyer* did little to help bilingual education in the actual era in which it was decided. At best, it solidified the right of people to speak their preferred language in private only⁴⁰. In the period between World War I and the Great Depression, public animosity toward immigrants far outweighed any symbolic influence the Supreme Court could

³⁵ García Gorrido and Álvarez 46.

³⁶ *Ibid.*

³⁷ *Ibid.*

³⁸ *Meyers v. Nebraska* 262 U.S. 390 (1923)

³⁹ Crawford, “Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era.”

⁴⁰ García, O 149.

wield. The 1920s saw the passage of dramatic federal prohibitions on immigration from Asia, south and central Europe, and explicitly showed preference to immigrants from northern Europe⁴¹. From 1890 to 1940, the language question on the Census served as a barometer that Congress used to determine whether it should raise or lower its immigration quotas, and the decision was consistently the latter⁴². As immigration was stifled, so too was the spread of non-English languages. In the period between the first and second world wars, many scholars have argued that bilingual education was “virtually eradicated” in its entirety⁴³.

Until the end of World War II, immigration and multilingualism were so effectively suppressed that there is almost no scholarship at all documenting the development of multilingualism during this period. English had gained such an exclusive hold on American society that foreign languages ceased being a policy issue altogether⁴⁴. In fact, the Census Bureau eliminated its language question at the start of World War II because it had simply lost its legislative relevance⁴⁵.

By the end of the Second World War, nativists had won their own war so decisively that the American campaign for linguistic assimilation exchanged its militaristic character for a more pitious one⁴⁶. Instead of a sign of national disloyalty, the inability to speak English began to be treated as a disability, especially for children⁴⁷. Teaching English to new immigrants was far from a priority, but it was at least respected as a charitable pursuit. At the start of the Cold War, the tone surrounding bilingualism finally changed as it became viewed as a national asset “for

⁴¹ Leeman 26

⁴² *Ibid.*

⁴³ Crawford, “Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era.”

⁴⁴ Leeman 26

⁴⁵ *Ibid.*

⁴⁶ Crawford, “Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era.”

⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

defense purposes⁴⁸.” For the first time since the 19th century period of linguistic salutary neglect, multilingualism became appreciated in schools and society because it could serve a “benefit to the United States government⁴⁹.” Importantly, though this justification for expanded bilingual education was perhaps less noble (there was no concern, of course, for preserving native languages of immigrants), it was far more sustainable⁵⁰. The idea that one could be a better government servant if they spoke multiple languages meant that language education could get long-term financial support from this very government.

By the 1960s, another benefit that arose for bilingual education was the Civil Rights Movement, which not only raised attention on issues of diversity but also led to the federal government playing a more active role in education as a whole⁵¹. Like the concurrent Civil Rights Movement, the growth of bilingual education began with the federal government’s acknowledgement that federal intervention was required—state and local governments, no matter how many laws were passed by Congress, would never adequately provide linguistic minorities with English education on their own⁵². Unlike the Civil Rights Movement, however, the government reform of bilingual education was viewed as an issue of “pedagogical effectiveness,” not equality⁵³. Under this reasoning, Congress passed what still remains bilingual education’s greatest victory in American history: the Bilingual Education Act of 1968. This act allocated substantial sums of federal funds that allowed the formation of effective, widespread education for learners of English nationwide. Nonetheless, it was still a product of its era. Though viewed skeptically at the time (and favorably now by linguistic justice activists) as an attempt to promote

⁴⁸ García, O 149.

⁴⁹ *Ibid.*

⁵⁰ *Ibid.*

⁵¹ Moran, Rachel F. “The Politics of Discretion: Federal Intervention in Bilingual Education.” *California Law Review*, vol. 76, no. 6, 1988, pp. 1249–352, <https://doi.org/10.2307/3480675>.

⁵² *Ibid.*

⁵³ *Ibid.*

permanent bilingualism, it was not⁵⁴. Instead, it was simply an earnest effort by the federal government to promote transitional bilingualism, which allowed foreign languages until English could be properly learned⁵⁵. Texas Senator Ralph Yarborough did not mince words to justify his support for the bill: “My purpose in doing this is not to keep any specific language alive... but just to try and make these children fully literate in English⁵⁶.” From this quote, one can learn volumes about this period of American linguistic history. First, it cements the legislation’s intention to promote transitional bilingualism, which is still the dominant form of education today. Second, it lends perspective on public opinion of bilingual education at the time: Senator Yarborough had to all but apologize in order to vote for the bill.

As the progressive Johnson administration passed the torch to Richard Nixon in 1969, it was extremely likely that these early multilingual reforms would be trampled by a cost-cutting administration. Instead, the “federal interest in bilingual schooling not only survived, but burgeoned, during the Nixon-Ford years⁵⁷. As the 1970s began, Nixon’s Department of Health, Education and Welfare (HEW) required school districts with large numbers of English learners to be equipped with bilingual education programs⁵⁸. Instead of backing away from the landmark Bilingual Education Act, the Nixon administration doubled down.

After earning victories in the legislative and executive branches, bilingual education was again tested in the judiciary. In 1974, the Supreme Court case of *Lau v. Nichols* questioned whether non-English-speaking Chinese-Americans in San Francisco were entitled to bilingual education under the Civil Rights Act of 1964⁵⁹. In response to the class action suit of about 1,800

⁵⁴ García, O 150.

⁵⁵ *Ibid.*

⁵⁶ *Ibid.*

⁵⁷ Davies 1406.

⁵⁸ *Ibid.*

⁵⁹ *Lau v. Nichols* 414 U.S. 53 (1974)

Chinese-American students, the Court's ruling was unanimous: the right to education is extended to all children, and under the status quo "students who do not understand English are effectively foreclosed from any meaningful education⁶⁰." Congress and the Nixon administration added a momentous expansion to this ruling with the Equal Education Opportunity Act of 1974, which extended *Lau's* authority to local and state control of schools as well ⁶¹.

In 1975, the Office of Civil Rights issued a memorandum seeking to materialize the mandated reforms of *Lau* that became infamously known as the "*Lau* remedies."⁶² Prospects for bilingual education were more optimistic than ever as it (miraculously) enjoyed public and governmental support. Unfortunately, enforcement challenges emphatically extinguished this brief string of victories for multilingualism in the United States. The *Lau* remedies outlined a requirement that districts with populations of non-English-speaking children of 5 percent or higher must institute voluntary programs of bilingual education⁶³. Problematically, these mandates called for a growth of classroom resources during a period of economic recession⁶⁴. This meant that schools with very limited numbers of teachers were put in an impossible scenario. On one hand, schools could only afford to provide bilingual classes by consolidating their non-English-speaking students⁶⁵. On the other, the language of the *Lau* remedies explicitly prohibited this consolidation because it was functionally resegregation⁶⁶. Thus, the guidelines set forth by the Nixon administration were ambitious but entirely infeasible. When the demanding character of the *Lau* remedies surfaced, public opinion regarding bilingual education soured. Noble as their intentions were, these remedies had called for reform that was astronomically

⁶⁰ *Ibid*, at 566.

⁶¹ Moran 1275.

⁶² García, O 151.

⁶³ *Ibid*.

⁶⁴ Stewner-Manzanares, Gloria. "The Bilingual Education Act: Twenty Years Later." *NCBE*, No. 6, 1998.

⁶⁵ *Ibid*, page 4.

⁶⁶ *Ibid*.

expensive. One school, for example, hosted non-English-speaking students from 21 distinct language groups⁶⁷. Under the guidelines of the *Lau* remedies, this school was mandated to hire native speakers to implement transitional bilingual programs for every one of these language groups⁶⁸. After half a decade of congressional battles over this unpopular mandate, the *Lau* remedies were abandoned entirely in 1981⁶⁹. The Reagan administration strongly emphasized federal deregulation, and this included bilingual education programs. Consequently, power over bilingual education was largely returned to local and state governments and funding for bilingual education fell by 25 percent⁷⁰. The fleeting golden age of American bilingual education had come to a close.

With public opinion turning broadly conservative and national support for multilingualism at an all-too-familiar low, California Senator S.I. Hayakawa entered the scene. Though a linguist, native of Canada, and victim of Japanese internment, Senator Hayakawa was no friend to multilingualism⁷¹. In 1981, he introduced a formal constitutional amendment that would make English the country's national language⁷². This bill never advanced beyond committee hearings, but Hayakawa did not abandon the effort. Two years later, he founded the U.S. English organization with the aforementioned polarizing white nationalist Dr. John Tanton⁷³. As will be discussed in later sections, U.S. English still exists today and reports a potentially dubious count of 2 million members⁷⁴.

⁶⁷ *Ibid*, page 6.

⁶⁸ *Ibid*.

⁶⁹ *Ibid*.

⁷⁰ *Ibid*.

⁷¹ "S.I. Hayakawa, 85, dies; challenged '60s radicals," *Los Angeles Times*, 28 Feb. 1992.

⁷² S.J. Res. 72.

⁷³ García Gorrido and Álvarez 47.

⁷⁴ "Support for Official English Remains Strong Among 73% of Americans." *U.S. English*, 7 May 2021, <https://www.usenglish.org/support-for-official-english-remains-strong-among-73-of-americans/>.

During the Reagan administration, Hayakawa's sentiments were shared by many. Amidst a wave of renewed immigration restrictions in 1984, Congress seriously considered adopting English proficiency as a prerequisite for permanent residency, though ultimately opted against this in the House of Representatives⁷⁵. In 1985, only a decade after the apex of bilingual education support in the wake of *Lau*, Secretary of Education William Bennett advocated for the complete elimination of bilingual instruction⁷⁶. In his view, the "sink or swim" approach, which saw English as the only appropriate language for immigrants to speak in school, was preferable.⁷⁷ Writing in the mid-1980s about the state of bilingual education, renowned linguistic researcher Ofelia Garcia identified a discontent that was almost identical to the waves of nativism displayed during World War I: "the promotion of a non-English language even as a temporary measure is seen as divisive since it emphasizes loyalty to the old country."⁷⁸ Bilingualism again became an issue of national allegiance. With this as the dominant political narrative, Garcia's prognosis of bilingualism-- in both natural and learned form-- was extremely bleak:

"The United States has never been successful in promoting bilingualism in schools. Although learned bilingualism is favored by most Americans as an enrichment activity, it is very difficult to achieve within a society that always equates bilingualism with disloyalty and foreignness... Bilingualism in the United States will remain a rare phenomenon, unless it is promoted for both the majority and the minority⁷⁹."

Such fears proved to be well justified during the 1990s. The legislative projects designed in the 1970s ostensibly designed to demonstrate the benefits of bilingual education could not produce enough success to endorse such a program on a larger scale⁸⁰. Without external political forces, opinion surrounding bilingual education may have slipped to indifference. Instead, it became

⁷⁵ García Gorrido and Álvarez 47.

⁷⁶ *Ibid.*

⁷⁷ *Ibid.*

⁷⁸ *Ibid.*

⁷⁹ García, O 156.

⁸⁰ Davies 1426.

linked with the prevailing “inflammatory rhetoric” of the day in the face of immigration debates of the 1990s. Before the presidential election of 1996, the House of Representatives summarily voted to end the program for bilingual ballots⁸¹. As the 20th century drew to a close, it had become evident that the national opinion surrounding bilingual education had peaked only momentarily before free-falling back to its original perception: a threat to the American way.

Entering the 21st century, two polar opposite characterizations of the state of bilingual education could both be considered accurate. On one hand, America’s shift toward conservatism and greater contentiousness regarding ethnic issues had placed bilingual education under “strong attack⁸².” As a whole, multilingualism in the United States faced a string of defeats from the Reagan administration onward. Gone were the days where the “surprisingly progressive” Richard Nixon would quietly push forward language education in schools⁸³. For bilingual education to continue, it would have to persist against substantial resistance. Surprisingly, it did just that.

The second characterization of bilingual education in the 2000s centers around a program that had established its roots in American soil and— though it may have been prevented from growing— would not soon be eradicated. Certain foreign language issues did not make the national spotlight, which allowed lawmakers to make modest progress in language preservation. One such example was the Native American Languages Act of 1990, a law that recognized the inherent value in the existence of a large swath of minority languages and set a “positive orientation” for future linguistic relations between tribal governments and the federal government⁸⁴. In 2006, Congress approved a rare legislative victory for bilingualism by reviving

⁸¹ García Gorrido and Álvarez 50.

⁸² Davies 1426.

⁸³ *Ibid*, at 1427.

⁸⁴ Leeman 31.

multilingual ballot programs for at least another 25 years— a program under which the country still operates to this day⁸⁵. Most essential, however, to the persistence of bilingual education at the start of the 21st century was a trifecta of three groups of political actors that did immeasurably beneficial work behind the scenes while public, racialized showdowns took place on center stage⁸⁶. First, government employees at the Office of Civil Rights diligently ensured that issues of bilingual education were absorbed by Title VI of the Civil Rights Act, making multilingualism an irremovable, if underfunded, feature of federally-funded education⁸⁷. Second, from the 1970s onward, a substantial group of Latino activists and lawyers had united to bring violations of bilingual education before the courts to secure judicial protection of these newfound rights⁸⁸. Finally, federal judges were receptive to the arguments of these activists, providing a legal stimulus for multilingual education to continue expanding⁸⁹. In short, the story of 21st century American bilingual education is the story of an effort that routinely lost in public but occasionally made valuable strides behind closed doors.

It is these types of victories— unsatisfyingly private but substantial— that characterize the development of attitudes toward bilingual education in 2022. At an institutional level, the United States has largely integrated bilingual education into the status quo. The 2016 presidential campaign of Donald Trump saw a renewed wave of nativism prosper around the United States, and yet Trump’s fiery anti-immigrant, anti-Spanish rhetoric never stretched beyond empty declarations that only English should be spoken in the United States⁹⁰. In fact, 2016 was the very same year that California lifted its ban on bilingual education through the overwhelming passage

⁸⁵ García Gorrido and Álvarez 47.

⁸⁶ Davies 1426.

⁸⁷ *Ibid.*

⁸⁸ *Ibid.*

⁸⁹ *Ibid.*

⁹⁰ Goldmacher, Shane. “Trump’s English-only campaign.” *Politico*, 23 Sep. 2016, <https://www.politico.com/story/2016/09/donald-trumps-english-only-campaign-228559>.

of Proposition 58⁹¹. By 2019, leading language scholars argued that English only laws were “on the verge of extinction,” with only Arizona maintaining the once-universal statute⁹². Such social progress is consistent with the bureaucratic groundwork laid at the end of the 20th century— for example, an accumulation of helpful court rulings at district levels, the assurance of bilingual education inclusion in modern versions of the Civil Rights Act, etc.— but even to the informed observer, the dramatic shift in attitudes over the last two decades has been stunning. From 1998 to 2003 alone, support for bilingual education raised from 33 to 58 percent nationally⁹³. After the Trump administration opted not to turn its nativist crosshairs toward bilingual education in the late 2010s, support for basic forms of bilingual education became such a foregone conclusion that Gallup appears to have stopped asking the question entirely.

Although the fading resistance to bilingual education is significant when one considers the three centuries of English exclusivism that preceded it, multilingualism is still treated with a great amount of institutional indifference in the modern United States. Now that prohibitions against multilingualism have been lifted in 49 states, one would imagine that bilingual education could prosper like never before. In reality, it has largely stagnated. Nonetheless, before turning to the current state of multilingualism in America, it is useful to have a foundational knowledge of the history of bilingual education strategies within the classroom specifically. The question looms over linguistic reformers: if U.S. foreign language education is so ineffective, how exactly has it been taught in the first place?

⁹¹ Mitchell, Corey. “California Voters Repeal Ban on Bilingual Education.” *Education Week*, 8 Nov. 2016, <https://www.edweek.org/teaching-learning/california-voters-repeal-ban-on-bilingual-education/2016/11>.

⁹² Mitchell, Corey. “‘English-Only’ Laws in Education on Verge of Extinction.” *Education Week*, 23 Oct. 2019, <https://www.edweek.org/teaching-learning/english-only-laws-in-education-on-verge-of-extinction/2019/10>.

⁹³Kiefer, Heather Mason. “Does Bilingual Education Translate to Success?” *Gallup*, 8 July 2003, <https://news.gallup.com/poll/8782/does-bilingual-education-translate-success.aspx>.

B. The Evolution of Bilingual Education

As public opinion regarding bilingual education evolved, so too did the product inside the classroom. Occasionally, teaching strategies would develop as academic approaches surrounding multilingualism grew more sophisticated. More often, though, these strategies changed over time out of necessity due to external factors like public pressure or financial restrictions. Indeed, the fact that bilingual education existed in the 18th and 19th centuries only because the federal government was not concerned enough to prevent it is a clear sign that multilingualism lacked the institutional support to sprout into a dynamic field of academia. As a result, this section heavily focuses on the variety of approaches taken to promote bilingual education from 1900 onward. In general, all bilingual education from its inception to the present has been designed to help students classified with Limited English Proficiency (LEP).

All types of education prior to the 20th century were almost entirely local. Teaching was viewed as an unattractive profession that was not suitable for educated adults, and certainly not worth a substantial government salary⁹⁴. This localized structure allowed bilingual education to exist and grow in the 19th century. In fact, by 1900, well over 200,000 children in the Midwest received their education in German⁹⁵. Contrary to their 20th century counterparts, these parochial bilingual schools were primarily immigrant-driven, designed both to retain culture and promote education in a way that was more accessible to those with English as a second language⁹⁶. Importantly, this is not to say that these parochial schools primarily existed for new immigrants to learn English. Instead, they offered an option for immigrants that struggled with English to

⁹⁴ Parkerson, Donald and Jo Ann Parkerson. *Transitions in American Education: A Social History of Teaching*, Taylor & Francis, 5 March 2014.

⁹⁵ Crawford. "Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era."

⁹⁶ *Ibid.*

sidestep this language barrier and receive an education regardless. Needless to say, the earliest forms of bilingual education were far from standardized.

As education became nationalized in the early 1900s, bilingual schools were eliminated and their students were placed into traditional public schools⁹⁷. As “frenetic patriotism” reigned in the wake of World War I, the daily experience of these students was so hostile that they were regularly punished for speaking native languages⁹⁸. Unsurprisingly, this tactic proved ineffective in raising levels of English proficiency among immigrant students and established a culture of school segregation prompted by language that impacted interracial interactions in the community at large⁹⁹. For four decades, this assimilation-through-education approach persisted and was applied indiscriminately, unconcerned of whether the child’s native language was German or Mandarin¹⁰⁰. Moreover, students who could not master English in this “sink or swim” environment were prevented from advancing in school, “required to stay back in the same grade until they became proficient¹⁰¹.” Such a process was rarely easy, and rarely short.

After World War II, the federal government moved toward a teaching style that is known among scholars as “missionary-style assimilation¹⁰².” There was little doubt that English was dominant in the United States, so students who could not speak English were seen as disadvantaged rather than threatening. Though condescending in nature, this “missionary” approach authored major strides for the education of students with Limited English Proficiency (LEP)¹⁰³. In lieu of the notorious “sink or swim” approach, “pullout classes” were formed that

⁹⁷ Osborne 8.

⁹⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹⁹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁰ “History of Bilingual Education.” *FindLaw*, 20 Jun. 2016, <https://www.findlaw.com/education/discrimination-harassment-at-school/history-of-bilingual-education.html>.

¹⁰¹ *Ibid.*

¹⁰² Crawford. “Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era.”

¹⁰³ *Ibid.*

gave LEP students individualized English instruction for approximately 45 minutes a day to develop their linguistic skills directly¹⁰⁴. Moreover, the government began implementing instruction that accounted for English proficiency as a distinct entity, rather than simply placing all LEP students in remedial reading classes¹⁰⁵. For the first time in American history, there was at least a semblance of an acknowledgement that limited English proficiency did not mean limited intelligence.

In 1958, two events related to the Cold War had a direct impact on language classrooms. First, the Soviet Union's successful launch of the satellite Sputnik heightened the tensions of the war so greatly that it impacted public school curriculum in math, science, and foreign language¹⁰⁶. Apparently, the prospect of a global war spurred the desire to raise a new generation of globally literate Americans. Second, the Cuban Revolution sent scores of refugees to southern Florida, which laid the groundwork for somewhat of an educational miracle. To accommodate the influx of Cuban immigrants, a large number of Spanish-English bilingual schools were established and gained national attention in a matter of five years for their unique effectiveness in a United States whose LEP programs were largely unsuccessful¹⁰⁷.

The failure of the nation's bilingual programs outside of Florida would surprise no one who is familiar with the process of language acquisition. Even among programs with resources, schools rushed students through English instruction and had little room to help children who struggled. This resulted in the production of many "half-lingual children: stutters in thought, stammerers in spirit¹⁰⁸." When programs tried to move slower to accommodate this, they risked

¹⁰⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁶ Escamilla, Kathleen. "A Brief History of Bilingual Education in Spanish." *ERIC Clearinghouse on Rural Education and Small Schools*, 1989, <https://www.ericdigests.org/pre-9211/brief.htm>.

¹⁰⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁰⁸ Crawford. "Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era."

leaving students behind in other subjects¹⁰⁹. This no-win structure yielded abysmal results. In the diverse boroughs of New York City in 1963, a grand total of 1 percent of Puerto Rican students graduated from high school¹¹⁰. Among tens of thousands of students, only 28 would go on to college¹¹¹. Unbelievably, this was one of the country's more positive case studies in multilingual education. In the heavily-Latino southern states of California, Texas, Colorado, Arizona and New Mexico, only 5.5 percent of Mexican-American children were enrolled in classes for English learners¹¹². Results may have been unsightly for New York's poorly funded programs, but the majority of Spanish-speakers in the South lacked any programs at all.

It took a poetic storm of impressive successes in Florida and staggering failures elsewhere to finally gain the attention of Congress, and even this may have fallen short if not for the ongoing Civil Rights Movement. Fortunately for bilingual education, the Civil Rights Movement had reached its apex. In 1968, Congress combined no less than 38 individual bills into one behemoth: the Bilingual Education Act¹¹³. This act, also known as Title VII of the Elementary and Secondary Education Act (which is discussed at length in Part II), was the first federal acknowledgement that English language education was necessary for "equal education opportunity," and as a result, required substantial federal funding¹¹⁴. Moreover, it began encouraging instruction in foreign languages for English speakers, a borderline revolutionary concept for the mid-20th century¹¹⁵. In accordance with the law, Congress appropriated over \$7 million to bilingual education and federally-funded programs opened its doors to 27,000 new students. After approximately 200 years, the first steps could be taken inside the classroom.

¹⁰⁹ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹¹² *Ibid.*

¹¹³ Stewner-Manzanares 1.

¹¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁵ *Ibid.*

After 1968, all conversations about the evolution of bilingual education in the United States would start and end with the Bilingual Education Act (BEA). Over the next two decades alone, the act was majorly restructured four times. The first amendment came in 1974 when it was clear that the well-intentioned first edition of the BEA needed much greater detail and much greater funding. Congress set specific goals for federal bilingual education programs and connected them with their initiatives to promote equality in education¹¹⁶. They also recognized that programs teaching English as a second language were “insufficient,” emphasizing instead the need for a substantial reliance on native language instruction, particularly for core subjects¹¹⁷. Bilingual education could no longer be viewed as a supplement to a traditional English education, but rather its own distinct process. Lastly, the 1974 version of the BEA established a variety of tangible resources: regional support centers, trainers, a national information hub dedicated to bilingual education, etc¹¹⁸. Most importantly, Congress took a financial leap. Funding for the BEA soared from \$7 million to \$68 million, raising the number of students served from 27,000 to well over 330,000¹¹⁹.

As bilingual programs grew, philosophies over the appropriate purpose for these programs began to diverge sharply. It was hotly debated whether bilingual education programs should exist to help preserve native cultures or simply to aid in assimilation¹²⁰. Would a “successful” bilingual education create a fully bilingual student? Or would it create a student who was fully, monolingually proficient in English (with their native language eradicated)?¹²¹. These questions began to materialize into an answer by the 1978 amendment to the BEA, which

¹¹⁶ *Ibid.*, at 3.

¹¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹¹⁸ *Ibid.*, at 4.

¹¹⁹ *Ibid.*

¹²⁰ Escamilla.

¹²¹ *Ibid.*

once again expanded the breadth of the act but, this time, restricted its scope. On one hand, funding for the young program more than doubled from \$68 million to \$135 million, extending the BEA to “historically underserved students¹²².” On the other, it rather forcefully settled the debate of the appropriate nature of bilingual education programs. It was determined that “native language was to be used only to the extent necessary for students to become proficient in English.¹²³” If schools opted to promote native language maintenance for any reason, they were disqualified from federal funding¹²⁴. Perhaps the best framing of the educational strategy during this decade is that a substantial enthusiasm grew for one specific type of language education: teaching English.

During the 1970s and 80s, academic literature shared this enthusiasm and took major strides in studying the language acquisition process. New research emerged documenting the specific needs of students at different stages of language development, discouraging the treatment of teaching English as a monolithic process¹²⁵. This slew of research also warned of a greater need for patience among administrators, saying that children require approximately 2 years to become proficient in basic communication in a new language and approximately 6 years to become proficient in the language’s formal aspects¹²⁶. In stark contrast with the traditional “sink or swim” model, the research that dominated the 70s and 80s argued that students should still be given access to native language instruction even after reaching formal proficiency¹²⁷. Thus, academic opinion surrounding language education appears to have been insulated from the

¹²² Stewner-Manzanares 5

¹²³ *Ibid.*

¹²⁴ *Ibid.*

¹²⁵ Osborne 10-11.

¹²⁶ *Ibid.*

¹²⁷ Crawford, “Bilingual Education Traces Its U.S. Roots to the Colonial Era.”

deterioration of general public opinion surrounding bilingual education during the Reagan era (see Part I, Section A).

Inside the classroom, the 1980s represented a period of divergence among teaching strategies as federal policies began to promote flexibility. Congress substituted sweeping, unpopular *Lau* approach for a localized system of grants that resembled a better-funded version of the bilingual programs in the 19th century¹²⁸. In hopes to promote innovation, the federal government awarded grants to school districts that they believed to have the most effective English education strategies¹²⁹. The best of these institutions schools were listed as “model schools” by the government and, in return for federal funding, were expected to disseminate information to other bilingual programs on best practices in a type of compelled mentorship¹³⁰. The reformed federal attitude toward bilingual education was so much a reactive measure to direct government involvement that the text of the 1984 legislation even directly stipulated that parents were expected to “take a greater role in the education of LEP students¹³¹.” The new law added family literacy programs that gave instruction to LEP parents as well as children and generally emphasized the importance of sustained familial involvement¹³². To complement this added responsibility, parents were also given more autonomy, and were granted the right to remove their children from language education programs if they saw fit¹³³.

In addition, the passage of the 1984 and 1988 editions of the Bilingual Education Act also established a sense of financial stability in the programs. The acts authorized \$139 million and \$152 million, respectively, and cemented the legislation as a long-term staple in federal

¹²⁸ Stewner-Manzanares 5.

¹²⁹ *Ibid.*

¹³⁰ Stewner-Manzanares 7.

¹³¹ *Ibid.*

¹³² *Ibid.*

¹³³ *Ibid.*

funding of education¹³⁴. In a report published in the same decade as her contemporary Ofelia Garica, the New York professor who had serious doubts about the health of bilingual education moving forward, linguistic researcher Gloria Stewner-Manzanares concluded that, from an institutional and logistical perspective, the evolution of American bilingual education was following a generally positive trajectory. “Though the education of students with limited English proficiency has been controversial at times” she wrote, “it has evolved in an effort to better meet LEP students' needs¹³⁵.”

Beginning in the 1990s, literature and theory surrounding bilingual education began to materialize into the character it holds today. As funding stabilized, the field enjoyed another surge of research that targeted increasingly specific and innovative inquiries¹³⁶. For example, after decades of supporting only bilingualism in the context of English education, academics began to seriously debate the merits of English speakers acquiring a second language and non-native English-speakers retaining their first¹³⁷. It was in the 90s, as well, that the nation's first dual immersion and dual language programs gained meaningful traction, which will be discussed at length in Part III¹³⁸. It took no less than two centuries after the establishment of the United States for academia to consider supporting bilingualism for its own sake, but it was a meaningful victory nonetheless for multilingualism as the 21st century began. Today, nationwide bilingual education programs are abundant and the research is more abundant still. As of 2015, the U.S. Department of Education reported that nearly all of the 4.8 million students learning

¹³⁴ Stewner-Manzanares 7,9.

¹³⁵ Stewner-Manzanares 9.

¹³⁶ Osborne 11

¹³⁷ *Ibid.*

¹³⁸ *Ibid.*

English in the United States (97 percent) were enrolled in some type of language instruction program¹³⁹.

Despite these significant strides, bilingual classrooms remain primarily oriented to the purpose for which they have long existed: teaching students English as fast as possible. Perhaps the federal government now views bilingual students as a “tremendous asset,” but this is only if “their full potential can be unlocked and harnessed¹⁴⁰.” That is, only if they can learn English. For all the literature that has emerged regarding bilingual education, it is English, not any other language, that dominates the discussion. The United States may be a country that prides itself-- and even identifies itself-- on its diversity, but the exclusivity of English remains ingrained in its culture. Why then, has the exclusivity of English never been formally ingrained in national legislation as well? The final historical section of this paper examines this question, exploring the history of English’s storied failure to earn the status of America’s “official” language.

C. The Undeclared Designation of “Official”

Paradoxically, although a formidable resistance to bilingual education has always existed in the United States, so too has a formidable resistance existed against the establishment of English as the country’s national language. Though Benjamin Franklin notoriously attempted to make English the official language of both Pennsylvania and the U.S. colonies as a whole in 1750, this represents only half of the story. Franklin never won a vote to make English the official language of Pennsylvania or the soon-to-be United States. Though he founded many schools designed to promote the use of only English, German-American families withdrew their children from these schools and quickly set to work on establishing their own, bilingual

¹³⁹ “Our Nation’s English Learners.” *U.S. Department of Education*, <https://www2.ed.gov/datastory/el-characteristics/index.html#one>.

¹⁴⁰ *Ibid.*

institutions¹⁴¹. The behavior of Pennsylvania families in the mid-18th century is impressively emblematic of the rest of U.S. linguistic history: despite suffering extensive persecution, multilingualism has always been an irremovable feature of the United States. Indeed, the founding fathers had the opportunity to declare English the country's official language when drafting the Constitution and opted against it¹⁴². This was not by accident. Scholars have documented that even among the founding fathers there was “a belief in tolerance for linguistic diversity within the population, the economic and social value of foreign language knowledge and citizenry, and a desire not to restrict the linguistic and cultural freedom of those living in the new country¹⁴³.” Indeed, the motto *E pluribus unum* itself was an attempt by John Adams, Thomas Jefferson, and Franklin to “illustrate the various linguistic and cultural backgrounds of [America's] citizens¹⁴⁴.” Despite its history of discrimination, the United States has been quick to accept its characterization as a “melting pot”: an eclectic collection of states that is home to an eclectic collection of cultures¹⁴⁵.

It bears noting that the United States' decision to forego an official language makes it particularly unique among its global peers. As early as the foundation of the United Nations in the aftermath of World War II, the merit of legitimizing particularly popular languages was internationally accepted. In 1946, for example, the U.N. established five languages— English, French, Spanish, Russian, and Chinese— as its official languages¹⁴⁶. In 1980, as a nod of respect to the prominence of languages in southwestern Asia, Arabic was added to its list of official

¹⁴¹García Gorrido and Álvarez 45.

¹⁴² Lewelling 2

¹⁴³ *Ibid.*

¹⁴⁴García Gorrido and Álvarez 43.

¹⁴⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁴⁶ “What are the official languages of the United Nations?” *United Nations Dag Hammarskjöld Library*, 8 March 2022, <https://ask.un.org/faq/14463>.

languages¹⁴⁷. Such actions were important because they were implicit refutations of the somewhat foundational American idea that an eclectic mix of cultures was best accepted by an eclectic mix of languages, none of which can be official. The U.N., conversely, which is inherently multicultural and multilingual, saw fit to promote unity through the declaration of a handful of major languages as official. Thus, it would be far from abnormal for the multicultural United States to do the same with its own major language of English. Certainly, it would have been consistent with other countries. In fact, no less than 178 countries had declared official languages as of 2018¹⁴⁸.

Surprisingly, the attitude of the founding fathers was never substantially challenged until 1981, when Senator Hayakawa introduced the English Language Amendment¹⁴⁹. As though making up for two centuries of neglecting this issue, Senator Hayakawa's bill was a forceful rebuke of multilingualism. Beyond the symbolic gesture of making English the national language, the amendment would have also prevented all state or local laws and programs from requiring services to be available in multiple languages. In fact, it stipulated that no law could ever require documents to be translated in a language other than English¹⁵⁰. Though this bill proved unsuccessful at the federal level, it gained considerable traction among states. In 1986, Hayakawa's home state of California even adopted a measure declaring English its official

¹⁴⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁴⁸ Misachi, John. "Countries With the Most Official Languages." *World Atlas*, 17 Aug. 2018, <https://www.worldatlas.com/articles/which-country-has-the-highest-number-of-official-languages-in-the-world.html#:~:text=178%20countries%20worldwide%20have%20at,an%20official%20in%20that%20country..>

¹⁴⁹ Lewelling 2

¹⁵⁰ *Ibid.*

language¹⁵¹. Since then, California has been joined by 30 other states nationwide, thanks largely to persistent lobbying by organizations like Pro English, English First, and U.S. English¹⁵².

Of the organizations fighting for the passage of the English Language Amendment, U.S. English has been the most influential since its inception in the mid-1980s. The defense of the U.S. English Foundation in its rational form resembles a brand of “political idealism,” a patriotic harkening to Enlightenment ideals that “language and nation are inextricably intertwined,” and as a result, a national language is a form of great unity¹⁵³. Advocates for U.S. English frequently reference the idea of *E pluribus unum* for themselves, arguing that America’s great diversity necessitates an equally formidable unifier¹⁵⁴. Because a proficiency in English is indispensable for success in the United States, they argue, immigrants are benefitted by Official English policies because it will promote opportunities and incentives to learn the language they must learn¹⁵⁵. These arguments have proven persuasive to a considerable number of Americans and are even acknowledged by dissenting scholars to be broadly reasonable¹⁵⁶. Unfortunately, the arguments of U.S. English are rarely formatted as eloquent Enlightenment philosophy. Quite the contrary, U.S. English is burdened with the long history of “nativist attacks on minority languages and their speakers,” which are considered far more prominent manifestations of Official English¹⁵⁷.

¹⁵¹ Baron.

¹⁵² Grovum, Jake. “A Growing Divide Over Official-English Laws.” *Pew*, 8 Aug. 2014, <https://www.pewtrusts.org/en/research-and-analysis/blogs/stateline/2014/08/08/the-growing-divide-over-official-english-laws#:~:text=The%20result%20is%20a%20patchwork,English%20as%20their%20official%20languages>.

¹⁵³ Baron.

¹⁵⁴ “E Pluribus Unum: Out of Many, One: Why English as a common language is critical to America’s unity.” *U.S. English*, 2012, pp. 5 <https://usefoundation.org/wp-content/uploads/2016/10/EPluribusUnumBriefingFinal.pdf>.

¹⁵⁵ *Ibid.*

¹⁵⁶ Baron.

¹⁵⁷ *Ibid.*

Even when they are not overtly racist, arguments from U.S. English continue to be the subject of intense criticism. For example, in 2003 the trilingual chair of U.S. English, Mauro Mujica, abandoned abstract advocacy for national unity in an article for *The Globalist* and instead relied on bold claims that bilingual government translations “remove the incentive [for immigrants] to learn English” and cost “millions of dollars” that could otherwise be spent on English education¹⁵⁸. In the modern era, it is these implicitly discriminatory statements that engender the controversy around English as the national language. Perhaps, indeed, the majority of developed nations worldwide recognize their heritage language in some official capacity, but these efforts are rarely at the expense of their minority languages. In Sweden, for instance, it is hard to imagine an organization publishing an official report stating that translating medical documents is a form of “pandering to foreign language speakers” that allows them to “delay their assimilation¹⁵⁹.”

Due to this controversy, an organized resistance to U.S. English bloomed by 1987. After Senator Hayakawa’s English Language Amendment gained national attention at the start of the decade, an assortment of more than 50 civil rights groups formed the English Plus Information Clearinghouse (EPIC)¹⁶⁰. In contrast to its Official English opponents that existed for the purpose of legislative advocacy, EPIC was designed to be a centralized hub of information that would assist civil rights organizations in their resistance of Official English policies¹⁶¹. EPIC was founded under the principle that that non-English-speaking individuals in the United States suffered from a “lack of opportunity, not lack of motivation¹⁶². Ironically, many goals of EPIC

¹⁵⁸ Mujica, Mauro. “English: Not America’s Language?” *The Globalist*, 19 Jun. 2003, <https://www.theglobalist.com/english-not-americas-language/>.

¹⁵⁹ “E Pluribus Unum,” pg. 5.

¹⁶⁰ Lewelling 2

¹⁶¹ *Ibid.*

¹⁶² *Ibid.*

are identical to the stated goals of organizations like U.S. English. For example, both groups support a boosted federal investment in English education for LEP students¹⁶³. Both groups cite statistics that illustrate an overwhelming majority— over 90 percent— of Latin American immigrants believe that learning English is critical to success in the United States¹⁶⁴. The complex nature of American linguistic issues have caused the objectives of U.S. English and EPIC to align, two organizations that operate under polar opposite principles. Despite this somewhat humorous phenomenon, it is undeniable that the “English Plus” efforts of EPIC exist solely to oppose Official English influence. Fortunately for supporters of Official English, this resistance has proved more symbolic than tangible, as the height of English Plus victories compose only a modest collection of states that have passed formal resolutions saying that “proficiency in other languages should be encouraged” and that designating English as the national language is unnecessary¹⁶⁵.

The natural question remains: how, then, are Official English movements faring in 2022? They are certainly not defunct. In 2015, Iowa congressman Steve King introduced the English Language Unity Act in a late Obama-era bill that can be viewed in two ways¹⁶⁶. On one hand, the fact that King took a less bold approach than Hayakawa— turning to a mere congressional act instead of a constitutional amendment— and the relatively limited scope of the bill— which is largely symbolic with the exception of more stringent requirements to the naturalization process— lead to the conclusion that Official English movements are weakening¹⁶⁷. After all, the bill never progressed beyond committee hearings¹⁶⁸. On the other hand, King’s efforts indicate

¹⁶³ Lewelling 3

¹⁶⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁵ Lewelling 5

¹⁶⁶ United States, Congress, House. English Language Unity Act of 2015. Congress.gov, 114th Congress, H.R. 997, Introduced 13 Feb. 2015.

¹⁶⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁶⁸ *Ibid.*

that a not insignificant share of Americans believe in the principles of Official English enough for it to be politically savvy to introduce a bill. Though their influence may be limited and their legislative efforts rarely successful, Official English is far from instinct in the United States.

PART II: POLICY

“We should replace bilingual education with immersion in English so people learn the language of prosperity... not the language of living in a ghetto.”

- U.S. Speaker of the House Newt Gingrich, 2007

A. Multilingualism and Current Education

Amelia Friedman was not the first journalist in American history to write a story slamming the United States for its lagging linguistic ability. In fact, only months after she published her critique in *The Atlantic* in 2015, the Obama administration passed a law that worked to reverse the damage of the No Child Left Behind Act of 2001, indicating that the failure of language education was no foreign concept to the American government¹. Nonetheless, Friedman’s article is emblematic of the recent, modest reawakening of the American public and government to the failure of linguistic education. Moreover, it outlines key reasons for the nationwide severity of the conditions that prompted such a reawakening to occur.

Because of the vestiges of the era of dynamic linguistic activism in the United States (which took place in late 20th century, see Part I), almost all American students will encounter some form of foreign language during their academic careers. As Friedman notes, 93 percent of American high schools alone offer foreign language courses². Such a statistic might lead one to an optimistic outlook: if so many students are taking rigorous language classes, won’t it simply be a matter of time before the United States starts making substantial linguistic progress?

Unfortunately, Friedman’s “93 percent” statistic comes with a glaring asterisk: less than 1

¹ “Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA)” *U.S. Department of Education*, <https://www.ed.gov/essa?src=rn>.

² Friedman.

percent of U.S. adults are proficient in a language they learned in a U.S. classroom³. This fact alone is devastating to multilingualism reform efforts, as they suggest that even if activists can garner a national will for expanded language education, this language education has no promise of being effective.

Even worse, U.S. foreign language education suffers from a breadth problem as well. While second languages might be offered in the high school setting, their availability is limited in all other classrooms. The National Education Association reports that only 25 percent of elementary schools and 58 percent of middle schools offer any type of foreign language classes at all⁴. This is particularly detrimental when one considers the psychosocial development of children, which has long dictated that “an early start provides an edge in acquiring language proficiency⁵.” At the collegiate level, prospects are even worse: only 7 percent of American college students are enrolled in a language course, meaning that roughly 18 of the 19.5 million college students across the country set foot in no classrooms that teach in a language other than English⁶. The harms of this nationwide language deficit are multifaceted, but perhaps the most alarming is the prediction of global scholars that the United States will soon lag so far behind in communicating with our global neighbors that we will need to import human capital in order to operate in cutting-edge fields like medicine or technology⁷.

In the face of such an overwhelming challenge of reform-- to say nothing of the overwhelming consequences of failure-- it has proven easy for casual observers to adopt an

³ *Ibid.*

⁴ Flannery, Mary Ellen. “As Need for Foreign Languages in School Grows, Access Continues to Shrink.” *National Education Association*, 13 Jan. 2017, <https://www.nea.org/advocating-for-change/new-from-nea/need-foreign-languages-school-grows-access-continues-shrink>.

⁵ *Ibid.*

⁶ Friedman.

⁷ *Ibid.*

attitude of resignation regarding American language education. Indeed, as described by prominent linguistic lobbyist Bill Rivers in an interview with Friedman: “It isn’t that people don’t think language education is important. It’s that they don’t think it’s possible.⁸” This attitude of catastrophism is complemented among Americans by an attitude of complacency. In a 2013 YouGov poll, only 43 percent of Americans believed it was “important” for any person to learn a second language simply for the sake of knowing the language⁹. In this same poll, more than a quarter of respondents saw bilingualism as unnecessary because “most people they know speak English¹⁰.”

As described in Part I, the late-20th century saw Americans wrestle with the question of whether bilingual education should exist solely to teach English to non-English-speakers or whether it wielded enough merit to be considered important for English-speakers as well. The answer to this question has shaped the grim multilingualistic reality that governs the United States today. Influenced by centuries of linguistic discrimination, the public remains largely persuaded by the idea that non-English education is at best unnecessary and at worst dangerous. Scholars have documented that all policy related to bilingual education is “unavoidably linked” with issues of ethnic identity, meaning that, to this day, policymakers who want to wade into the waters of language education reform must also travel through an ocean of identity politics¹¹. Herein lies the most important component to understanding the current policy toward language education: bilingual programs are, and have always been, shaped by social and political factors “distinct from the educational needs of the children they serve¹².”

⁸ *Ibid.*

⁹ Palmer, Kate. “75% of Americans have no second language.” *YouGov America*, 31 July 2013, <https://today.yougov.com/topics/lifestyle/articles-reports/2013/07/31/75-americans-have-no-second-language>.

¹⁰ *Ibid.*

¹¹ Osborne 12, translated.

¹² Osborne 12, translated.

Though resilient from their survival of decades of campaigns geared toward their eradication, the bilingual programs that remain in the United States presently face two principal challenges: unavoidable costliness and sustained misinformation. First, it must be acknowledged that bilingual programs are inherently more expensive to implement than traditional English-only classrooms. Multilingual instructors are considered specialized teachers (and often possess advanced degrees), which commands a higher salary¹³. The development of foreign language or bilingual course materials is also very costly, leaving schools to either pay a premium for textbooks for a limited population or equip students with out-of-date or incomplete materials, neither of which is ideal¹⁴. When one considers that education funding is already subject to extreme limitations, the challenge of convincing a school board to increase bilingual budgets can appear insurmountable. Second, national understanding of multilingualism, especially in children, is riddled with misconceptions. A variety of misguided studies rose to prominence in the 20th century concluded that bilingualism undermines “cognitive and linguistic development because the brain cannot simultaneously register multiple linguistic pathways¹⁵.” As will be discussed in Part III, the idea that multilingualism stunts linguistic development is patently false. Nonetheless, it is a popular misconception that has persisted for more than a century. Consequently, policymakers to this day see bilingual education as not only an unpatriotic promotion of dual loyalty, but also a promotion of costly and ineffective education.

Unfortunately, the public is not the only group that suffers from linguistic misconceptions. Poorly-informed perspectives abound even among well-intentioned policymakers who seek to encourage the shift toward more “inclusionary policies” regarding

¹³ Osborne 15.

¹⁴ Osborne 14.

¹⁵ Osborne 9.

American language identities in the classroom¹⁶. All language laws since the Civil Rights Movement have been centered around the explicit or implicit belief that minority languages are “social problems roughly equivalent to poverty or substandard housing¹⁷.” Even for lawmakers who pass the law in order to promote greater diversity and language equity, this fails to promote multilingualism for a number of reasons. First, it only reinforces the “negative portrayal” of languages other than English¹⁸. Laws that operate under the “language-as-problem” approach inherently communicate that the very existence of other languages is the problem. In a society where language and ethnoracial identity are inextricably linked, such linguistic biases can manifest themselves as discrimination against the speakers themselves¹⁹. Second, modern “language-as-problem” laws do little to resist what scholars call the “hegemonic centrality of English²⁰.” In simpler terms, education systems that are indifferent to native language retention foster an environment where native languages simply die from neglect. Rates of monolingualism skyrocket from first to second generation immigrants, and by the third generation, English is spoken almost exclusively²¹. Thus, while certain individuals may escape the harmful effects of English hegemony, a cycle of monolingualism is perpetuated.

Taken in their totality, these realities surrounding language classrooms point strongly to the idea that language reform is not primarily an issue of budget increases or building schools, but rather cultural change. In the current model, bilingual education faces such substantial obstacles that it would require immense financial patience and political consistency to implement in a way that generates more positive outcomes. In questions of government funding, patience is

¹⁶ Leeman 31.

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ *Ibid.*

²¹ Skapinker.

almost always in short supply. When bilingual programs yield predictably unflattering results, the group that most often bears the cultural blame is the state and local educators²². Linguistic minority parents, community activists and federal civil rights officials alike most often rely on quality of teaching as a scapegoat that justifies systemic reorganization, upending local bilingual programs on a regular basis before they could realistically have grown to be effective²³.

Sometimes, however, as in the 1960s and 70s, the natural vacillation of American politics permits a period of economic prosperity that opens a window for financial patience. In the 20th century, this brief period of patience made bilingual programs— amidst all of their flaws— fixtures of the American education system. When these rare periods of patience materialize, scholars must turn to the next question: how can one reach sufficient political consistency to prevent the uprooting of fledgling bilingual programs? How, especially, can the American government do so during a time of historic polarization? In an attempt to answer this question, the following section will trade the linguistic perspective on language reform for one that is purely political.

B. Multilingualism and Politics

The advantage of a political perspective on language reform is its capacity for simplification. While social and linguistic considerations of bilingual education in the United States seem to boast an overwhelming number of landmark events, policy considerations can be reduced to a few formative federal laws and a handful of unpassed bills that wielded cultural influence. To be specific, four laws influence the current policy landscape of bilingual education: the Elementary and Secondary Education Act (ESEA) of 1965, the Bilingual Education Act

²² Moran 1315.

²³ *Ibid.*

(BEA) of 1968, the No Child Left Behind Act (NCLB) of 2001, and most recently, the Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA) of 2015. Each will be discussed in turn.

The ESEA and BEA are, as alluded to in Part I, the closest political blueprints available for a progressive stance on language reform. They represent the only time in American history when a generous amount of money was granted to bilingual education, the only time when native language retention was ever briefly considered, and the only period in which bilingual education enjoyed steady support (lasting approximately 3 decades)²⁴. This “golden age” of language education also demonstrated the most effective long-term strategy that lasts beyond periods of capricious political support: generating research. In fact, of the English Plus movement’s modest number of victories— four, as of publication of this paper— would not have been possible without research on bilingual education that portrayed the programs in a positive light during the late 20th century²⁵.

Conversely, the NCLB Act is arguably the most effective blueprint for stymying bilingual education short of only eliminating it entirely. From this policy, it became clear that English Only advocates can be effective without gaining direct (and largely unfeasible) legislative victories, as their ever-present rhetoric engenders political agitation toward language that leads to budget-slashing programs like the NCLB²⁶. As a foil to the way that academic literature can set bilingual-friendly attitudes into motion, English Only figures can emotionally link language education to immigration in ways that make average Americans feel bilingual education is a form of political radicalism. The NCLB shows that opponents of bilingual education are wise to

²⁴ Stewner-Manzanares 1-9.

²⁵ Lewelling, Vickie. “English Plus.” *ERIC Clearinghouse on Languages and Linguistics*, 1997, <https://web.archive.org/web/20080724024953/http://www.cal.org/resources/archive/digest/1992englishplu.html>.

²⁶ Crawford, James. “A nation divided by one language.” *The Guardian*, 8 Mar. 2001, <https://www.theguardian.com/theguardian/2001/mar/08/guardianweekly.guardianweekly11>.

take advantage of the natural waves of nativism that engulf the U.S. about every half century, making backlash against bilingual education a cultural staple. Indeed, it was no coincidence that America's "golden age" of bilingual development was followed by a law that almost instantaneously reversed the progress of the previous two laws and made English Only the de facto federal stance on schools²⁷.

Last, the ESEA reflects both the position in which bilingual education sits in the modern day and the existence of an alternative to progress or regression: political stagnation. On one hand, in name alone it is a rebuke of NCLB. "No Child Left Behind," though certainly evoking emotions of ambition and heroism, unavoidably communicates a sense of proper uniformity: the implicit assumption is that the child that does not learn English is a child left behind. On the contrary, the name "Every Student Succeeds" implies a greater degree of flexibility, communicating a willingness to work from a bottom-up approach that starts with students. This is precisely how the act was communicated as well. The ESSA is a law that is highly local in nature and it helps bilingual education in a manner similar to the 19th century period of linguistic salutary neglect: the absence of federal government interference (and aggressive promotion of English) provides a significant boost that allows these programs to thrive²⁸. On the other hand, a lack of federal interference also represents a lack of federal support, leaving many bilingual programs unable to expand to meet the needs of their populations simply on account of a paucity of resources. Moreover, the federal branding of the act was largely marketed to Americans as a continuity of NCLB's attitude regarding language education: bilingual contexts are only appropriate so English can be learned²⁹. Depicted below is a chart from linguistic researcher

²⁷ Osborne 13.

²⁸ "Every Student Succeeds Act (ESSA)" *U.S. Department of Education*, <https://www.ed.gov/essa?src=rn>.

²⁹ Chang, Michelle. "English-As-a-Solution in the Elementary and Secondary Education Act (1968), No Child Left Behind Act (2002), and Every Student Succeeds Act (2015): Need for the Reimagination of English in the Us Education System." *University of Georgia*, 2020, pp. 18.

Michelle Chang that illustrates the fundamental similarities between the notorious NCLB Act and the ostensibly-better ESSA³⁰:

	Elementary and Secondary Education Act (1968)	No Child Left Behind Act (2002)	Every Student Succeeds Act (2015)
Title of Act	<i>Bilingual Education Act</i>	<i>English Language Acquisition, Language Enhancement, and Academic Achievement Act</i>	<i>English Language Acquisition, Language Enhancement, and Academic Achievement Act</i>
Title of Target Students	Children of <i>limited English-speaking ability</i> (LESA) & Children of <i>limited English proficiency</i> (LEP)	<i>Limited English proficient</i> children (LEP)	<i>English learners</i> (EL)
Title of Office	Office of <i>Bilingual Education and Minority Languages Affairs</i>	Office of <i>English Language Acquisition, Language Enhancement, and Academic Achievement for Limited English Proficient Students</i>	Office of <i>English Language Acquisition</i>
Title of National Clearinghouse	National Clearinghouse for <i>Bilingual Education</i>	National Clearinghouse for <i>English Language Acquisition</i>	National Clearinghouse for <i>English Language Acquisition</i>

³⁰ Chang 18-19.

Perhaps most apparent in the above chart is the shift from a primary purpose of “bilingual education” in 1968 to one of “English language acquisition” in 2002 and 2015. As a result, though the ESSA provided a symbolic step forward for the Obama administration on language policy— and in hot-button cultural issues like language, symbolic victories are substantial victories— it provided little practical aid to reverse the damage of the No Child Left Behind Act.

A survey of the political state of multilingualism, of course, must include more than just a review of Congress. In addition, it must be conscious of the general public opinion that shaped this policy. This raises several key considerations. Americans, as a body of democratic political actors, have decided to a seemingly irreversible degree that politics are mandatory in discussions of language: scholars tend to believe there will always be a prominent American voice arguing that “if you live in America, you need to speak English³¹.” Linguist James Crawford argues that the politicization of this subject “obscures the real debate about United States’ language policy,” which of course suggests that language policy may be condemned to a fate of eternal obscurity³². As a political body, too, Americans seem to have little motivation to tackle the persistent issue of linguistic misinformation. As quipped by Dr. Stephen Krashen, a linguistic researcher from the University of Southern California, “If all I knew about bilingual education was what I read in the newspapers, I’d vote against it too³³.” Dispelling misconceptions is a difficult enough task when the deceived parties seek the truth, but even Americans who are committed to fact-checking are unlikely to consider the politics of bilingual education to be worth any degree of critical thinking in the wake of a decades-long media blitz promoting the idea that bilingualism stunts language growth³⁴. And this grim obstacle says nothing of the Americans who believe their experience

³¹ Crawford, “A nation divided by one language.”

³² *Ibid.*

³³ *Ibid.*

³⁴ *Ibid.*

serves as confirmation of the harmfulness of bilingualism. Indeed, nearly 1 in 3 Americans living in the modern United States claim to be bothered by people speaking any language other than English in public³⁵. Even in 2022, American politics appear to adhere closer to the vestiges of its bygone, linguistically-hostile era than a diversity-minded acceptance of multilingualism.

³⁵ Skapinker.

PART III: INNOVATIVE SOLUTIONS

“While English continues to be the *lingua franca* for world trade and diplomacy, there is an emerging consensus... that proficiency in English is not sufficient to meet the nation’s needs in a shrinking world.”

- Conclusion of a 2017 study from the American Academy of Arts and Sciences

A. Other Countries Do It Better, But How?

If there is one reliable truth for researchers in the field of language reform, it is that the systems of other developed nations are always more effective than the United States. One can take any country in Europe and are almost assured a better linguistic performance than the United States. On a broad level, a staggering 92 percent of European students (K-12) are currently enrolled in a language class, drastically outpacing America’s 20 percent enrollment¹. Of course, European school systems face the same post-graduation dropoff that American systems do, but they still have managed to report a continental rate of bilingualism of about 56 percent, miles ahead of the United States’ measly 20 percent². This suggests that Europe not only operates at a higher baseline than the United States, but operates within a more effective system as well, where language education is designed to be more than a formality and bilingualism is culturally encouraged. On a more concentrated level, the European numbers grow more impressive. Seven European nations have an unfathomable 100 percent of their students enrolled in foreign language courses, and Europe’s lowest number of foreign-language-enrolled students (Belgium, at 64 percent) remains comfortably ahead of America’s best number (New Jersey, at

¹ Devlin.

² Mathews.

51 percent)³. On an institutional level, European language programs are significantly more practical and research-based. Their instruction in foreign language, for example, typically starts between the ages of six and nine⁴. This early start is particularly notable when one considers that one of the most well-established facts in linguistic research is that a child's brain is more receptive to learning a foreign language than an adolescent brain, suggesting that children should start foreign language education at age 10 or earlier⁵. Academic consensus notwithstanding, the typical American student will take their first foreign language class at age 14⁶. In every category, European language education and retention is decisively better than their American counterparts.

As overwhelming as these European figures are, they must be read with some hesitation. The landmass of the United States is close to that of the entire continent of Europe combined (excluding Russia)⁷. The United States accepts significantly more immigrants each year than any other country on earth, and does so from every corner of the globe⁸. Last, multilingualism is not a prerequisite to success in the world of American business as it is in Europe, meaning that the U.S. lacks Europe's financial incentive to maintain strong foreign language programs. In fact, only 36 percent of Americans even believe that multilingualism was a very important trait "to be successful in today's economy," a polling result that would almost certainly be impossible to

³ Devlin.

⁴ *Ibid.*

⁵ Hartshorne, Joshua. "Data: A Critical Period for Second Language Acquisition: Evidence from 2/3 Million English Speakers." *University of Chicago*, 12 Mar. 2018, <https://osf.io/pyb8s/>.

⁶ Pufahl et. al. "What We Can Learn from Foreign Language Teaching in Other Countries." *ERIC Clearinghouse on Languages and Linguistics*, 2001, <https://www.ericdigests.org/2002-2/countries.htm>.

⁷ Migrio, Geoffrey. "Are the USA And Europe The Same Size?" *World Atlas*, 26 Aug. 2019, <https://www.worldatlas.com/articles/usa-europe-same-size.html>.

⁸ "10 Countries That Take the Most Migrants." *U.S. News & World Report*, 24 Aug. 2021, <https://www.usnews.com/news/best-countries/slideshows/10-countries-that-take-the-most-immigrants>.

achieve across the Atlantic Ocean due to the extremely transnational nature of European business and trade⁹.

Nonetheless, the level of European success in language education is so convincing that it deserves at least a second glance, if not a detailed study, as a laboratory of innovation for language reform in the United States. While scholars and international language teachers have offered a plethora of explanations for the comparative European advantage regarding language, a handful of common themes routinely stand out: starting language education early (as previously described), establishing a uniform framework for language education across the country, implementing specialized training for language instructors, and encouraging bilingualism as a national priority, among other factors¹⁰. This section examines each of those factors in tandem with lesser-known factors that prove to have at least a somewhat substantial ability to foster a greater culture of multilingualism.

In 2001, Pufahl et. al published what still remains one of the most comprehensive descriptions of what separates the United States from their European peers linguistically. First, of course, is that other countries start language education at a routinely earlier age¹¹. Second, they outline that a nationalized approach to language education is indispensable in achieving nationalized results¹². This reasoning dictates that a well-articulated curriculum and uniform federal expectations in the United States could close the alarming gap between New Jersey's 51 percent rate of foreign language education and New Mexico's 9 percent¹³. On this issue, Pufahl's argument is not alone, as there is widespread scholar consensus that America's lack of "national-level mandates"-- and, indeed, its current trend toward further localization-- has made

⁹ Devlin.

¹⁰ Pufahl et. al.

¹¹ *Ibid.*

¹² *Ibid.*

¹³ Devlin.

language education a luxury that is subject to regional availability¹⁴. Third, instructors of foreign languages must be treated as those working in a “competitive,” “highly-valued profession¹⁵.” In stark contrast to America’s tendency to blame its foreign language instructors when performance of bilingual and English-learning programs are unsurprisingly poor, countries like the United Kingdom include specialized training designed to equip teachers for a job that they view carries an unparalleled importance¹⁶. In Finland, it is expected that teachers come from “among the best high school graduates,” representing an ability to capitalize on internal talent that far exceeds the United States¹⁷.

Fourth, speaking to the unifying theme of this entire paper: language education programs in Europe are treated with the respect-- and, at times, reverence-- of a national priority, while language programs in the U.S. are not. Pufahl et. al suggest a simple, though potentially unattainable, solution to this: “designate foreign language as a core subject¹⁸.” Fifth, a culture of multilingualism requires a culture where foreign language entertainment attains some degree of cultural relevance. In Denmark, for example, English and British TV shows and movies are so ubiquitous that students gain a valuable “informal foreign language exposure” on which their instructors can build¹⁹. To a modest degree, the phenomenon of informal foreign language education through entertainment has already established itself in the United States among the subculture of supporters of anime, or Japanese animated media²⁰. Particularly among younger generations, anime has spurred some monolingual Americans to develop a basic proficiency in

¹⁴ *Ibid.*

¹⁵ Pufahl et. al.

¹⁶ *Ibid.*

¹⁷ *Ibid.*

¹⁸ *Ibid.*

¹⁹ *Ibid.*

²⁰ Lai, Stephanie. “Kawaii! Americans Drop Japanese Into Conversations Learned From Cartoons.” *Wall Street Journal*, 22 Mar. 2022, <https://www.wsj.com/articles/japanese-language-learning-anime-manga-cartoons-comics-11647959639>.

Japanese solely to enjoy this beloved form of Japanese entertainment²¹. In some students, this basic proficiency lays the groundwork for further study and, after perhaps collegiate classes or study abroad opportunities, a path to fluency.

Finally, European countries are more accepting of programs that promote a retention of heritage languages, which creates a positive national sentiment toward bilingualism by associating it with multiculturalism²². Ironically, the opposite effect has occurred in the United States, as attempts to expand heritage language programs have been met with vocal accusations of national disloyalty (see Part II). In its best form however, these heritage language programs can be immensely effective and cost-efficient, as they draw on the natural resources that a country with a high immigrant population possesses. Beyond Europe, this policy has been fruitful in Canada as well, with several provinces able to maintain robust programs in not just English and French, but a variety of minority languages as well that correspond with their linguistic population²³. This is perhaps the most salient reform suggestion for the United States, as its prodigious population of Spanish speakers forms a remarkable opportunity for heritage programming. Already, Spanish is the language in the United States that appears to be most resistant to evaporation across generations, and this is largely due to the extensive community of Spanish speakers who encourage one another to retain their mother tongue²⁴. Moreover, by 2050, the United States will not just feature an extensive community of Spanish speakers, it will be the country with the most Spanish speakers in the world, with projections as high as 1 in 3 Americans having fluency in Spanish²⁵. Just as Europe capitalized on the linguistic resources in

²¹ *Ibid.*

²² Pufahl et. al.

²³ *Ibid.*

²⁴ Skapinker.

²⁵ Thompson, Sonia. "The U.S. Has The Second-Largest Population Of Spanish Speakers—How To Equip Your Brand To Serve Them." *Forbes*, 27 Mar. 2021,

its area by forming deeply connected networks of international trade, the United States, too, can take advantage of its linguistic resources and build robust education programs in Spanish.

Though not all linguistic solutions can come from overseas, it is certainly a practical place to start. Unfortunately, the unmatched diversity of the United States will also require a series of unmatched strategies for language education to even approach the levels of success that Europe and other developed nations have already enjoyed. This may sound like a daunting task, but one of the greatest features of the American reputation has long been its rich historical tradition of innovation. In this paper's final section, I examine some of the most ambitious ideas for language reform, outlining bold solutions and briefly discussing their relative feasibility in the United States over the coming decades.

B. Exploring Innovative Ideas

Amidst an era of stagnation for multilingualism, facing an English-favoring climate that is conducive to no new methods of bilingual education, one style of education has still blossomed. Since 2000, the popularity of dual immersion programs has soared at such an impressive rate that they demand to be the first topic of discussion in any conversation of language education reform. These programs-- known under many names ranging from "dual-language" to "two-way bilingual" programs-- operate under the general principle that students can learn a second language from kindergarten and that their core subjects can be taught in these languages²⁶. By design, these schools conduct about 90 percent of instruction in the "target" second language from the outset of a child's education. From there, the use of English slowly increases until fifth or eighth grade, typically peaking at a 50-50 split between target

<https://www.forbes.com/sites/soniathompson/2021/05/27/the-us-has-the-second-largest-population-of-spanish-speakers-how-to-equip-your-brand-to-serve-them/?sh=159b4156793a>.

²⁶Block, Nicholas. "The Impact of Two-Way Dual-Immersion Programs on Initially English-Dominant Latino Students' Attitudes." *Bilingual Research Journal*, vol. 34, issue 2, 2011, pp. 125-141.

language and English²⁷. The goals of these programs are simple: “academic achievement, bilingualism, and biculturalism,” painting themselves as the natural antithesis to a monolingual U.S. government that has only ever supported multilingual education as a means to teaching students English²⁸. Dual immersion programs operate under the conviction that language and its cultural associations are not simply a means to an end, but rather an end in and of itself. At the start of the 21st century, approximately 260 such programs existed in the United States²⁹. A decade later, that number ballooned to over 2,000, complemented by an impressive collection of academic literature citing the extensive benefits of these programs³⁰. That dual immersion programs could prosper at the apex of a cultural backlash against multilingualism is perhaps their most impressive feature. Writing for the *Harvard Education Letter* in 2011, David Wilson put it succinctly:

“At a time when other types of bilingual education are on the decline and the B-word—bilingual—has been scrubbed from the U.S. Department of Education lexicon, dual language programs are showing promise in their mission to promote biliteracy and positive cross-cultural attitudes in our increasingly multilingual world³¹.”

The aforementioned period of linguistic salutary neglect from the federal government that began in 2015 has helped this movement considerably, as nationwide estimates placed the number of schools at approximately 3,600 in 2021³². Unfortunately, due to the logistical obstacles of the coronavirus pandemic, exact figures in 2022 are not yet available. From the most optimistic

²⁷ *Ibid.*

²⁸ *Ibid.*

²⁹ Wilson, David McKay. “Dual Language Programs on the Rise.” *Harvard Education Letter*, vol. 27, no. 2, 2011.

³⁰ Gross, Natalie. “Dual-Language Programs on the Rise Across the U.S.” *Education Writers Association*, 3 Aug. 2016, <https://www.ewa.org/blog-latino-ed-bea/t/dual-language-programs-rise-across-us>.

³¹ Wilson.

³² Galván, Astrid. “U.S. sees explosion of dual-language programs.” *Axios*, 5 Apr. 2022, <https://www.axios.com/2022/04/05/explosion-dual-language-programs-spanish>.

standpoint, dual immersion programs represent the modern generation's iterations of the 19th century's resilient, locally-established bilingual institutions that worked to retain ethnic identity.

The exploding popularity of these programs is no coincidence, as the benefits of these programs on their students are extensive and well-documented. A 2015 study, for example, found that dual immersion students performed equally as well as their peers in traditional schools on English Language Arts (ELA) exams and outperformed their peers in mathematics³³. Another study showed improved standardized test results in science and social studies as well³⁴. Still another study found that English reading scores of dual immersion students significantly outpaced their English-only counterparts³⁵. Thus, dual immersion programs have proven to be beneficial for public education even if one does not even consider the linguistic benefits. To say nothing of the fact that graduates of dual immersion institutions typically develop bilingual proficiency-- a professional and personal asset in and of itself-- dual immersion programs have been shown to promote positive attitudes toward multiculturalism as well. In fact, even among individuals of Latin American descent, students who attended dual immersion institutions demonstrated a significantly greater appreciation of the Spanish language than their traditionally-educated counterparts³⁶. While this result may be intuitive, it comes with a variety of intangible benefits. These same students also described a more vocal appreciation of biculturalism and were much more comfortable speaking a foreign language in public, providing an eye-catching counter to one of America's most long standing attitudinal language problems³⁷.

³³ Watzinger-Tharp et. al. "Academic achievement of students in dual language immersion." *International Journal of Bilingual Education and Bilingualism*, vol. 21, issue 8, 2018, pp. 913-928.

³⁴"Bethesda Elementary School." *Georgia Governor's Office of Student Achievement*, <https://schoolgrades.georgia.gov/bethesda-elementary-school>.

³⁵ "Study of Dual-Language Immersion in the Portland Public Schools Year 4 Briefing: November 2015." *RAND Education*, https://www.pps.net/cms/lib8/OR01913224/Centricity/Domain/8/5/DLI_Year_4_Summary_Nov2015v7.pdf.

³⁶ Block.

³⁷ *Ibid.*

Less than a century after waves of nativism prompted intense public resistance of speaking non-English languages in public, dual immersion students are equipping students with the skill and confidence to do just that.

However, though appreciable for its unexpected success, the American dual immersion experiment is frozen in key structural limitations so long as they exist due to lack of institutional resistance instead of the presence of institutional support. Like many other historical obstacles of bilingual education, dual immersion programs are appealingly effective until the government tries to replicate them on any scale larger than local. These programs earn immense respect for operating at the height of a “monoglossic culture,” but the monoglossic culture that has made their ascent so impressive is the same one that places a firm ceiling on their ability to influence American language reform³⁸. To date, no federal bill has offered financial or even symbolic support to programs of dual immersion. Nonetheless, these programs have earned the attention and support of some state governments. California, for instance, appropriated \$10 million to be granted to these programs in 2022, with State Superintendent Tony Thurmond declaring that “increasing the number of multilingual programs throughout California is a key priority³⁹.” In 2015, the Department of Education in New York City sponsored the development of 40 additional dual immersion programs across the nation’s most populated city⁴⁰. In 2016, the District of Columbia Public School District declared a governmental commitment “guaranteeing that [all] students who wish to complete all of their pre-K-12 instruction in both Spanish and

³⁸ Williams, Conor. “A New Federal Equity Agenda for Dual Language Learners and English Learners.” *The Century Foundation*, 8 Dec. 2021, <https://tcf.org/content/report/new-federal-equity-agenda-dual-language-learners-english-learners/?session=1>.

³⁹ “2022 Request for Applications: Dual Language Immersion Grant.” *California Department of Education*, 4 Feb. 2022, <https://www.cde.ca.gov/nr/el/le/yr22ltr0204.asp#:~:text=2022%20Request%20for%20Applications%3A%20Dual%20Language%20Immersion%20Grant&text=Authorized%20under%20Assembly%20Bill%20130,fiscal%20year%20for%20the%20DLIG..>

⁴⁰ Gross.

English can do so in the school district⁴¹.” Though implementation challenges have certainly proven formidable, they have been far from insurmountable, leaving much room for optimism about the widespread applicability of these programs.

Beyond dual immersion programs, American language activists have a select number of other strategies at their disposal. Because much resistance to bilingual education comes not from right-wing nativist voices but from average, concerned parents who have internalized a narrative that bilingualism can hurt their child’s development, perhaps the most effective strategy for street-level activists would be to engage in information campaigns that rebrand the benefits of the language education process. One potential new “face” for bilingual development is that it fosters a complete, better-protected, more-powerful brain. Researchers at Michigan State University have found that bilingual children may have enhanced cognitive processing, exhibiting a “superior ability to focus on one thing and change their response” and greater flexibility in critical thinking⁴². Furthermore, these researchers concluded that bilingualism can protect against Alzheimer’s disease and other illnesses that deal with age-related mental deterioration, as though bilingual brains’ heightened processing capability also give them heightened defenses⁴³. Admittedly, statistics supporting the idea that bilingualism is beneficial have been ubiquitous for decades, so the key strategic decision comes not from the conclusions of these studies but rather how they are employed to win public support for multilingualism. To make the American system more like Europe’s, or at least to reshape popular perception of multilingualism, the public must undergo the painstakingly slow process of unlearning misconceptions. It must reverse the centuries-long, stigmatized association of bilingualism with

⁴¹ *Ibid.*

⁴² Trautner, Tracy. “Advantages of a bilingual brain.” *Michigan State University Extension*, 28 Jan. 2019, https://www.canr.msu.edu/news/advantages_of_a_bilingual_brain.

⁴³ *Ibid.*

mental division and confusion by providing ample messaging that associates bilingualism with a higher ability to perform academically and intellectually. The logistics of those public education campaigns are beyond the scope of this project, but the replacement of misinformation with cutting-edge studies is perhaps the most effective theoretical framework for promoting multilingualism. After all, multilingualism will prosper if the average American individual views it as something desirable, like achievement in math or science.

Moreover, these campaigns of reeducation must advertise more than just a greater capacity for intellectual development. Parents must hear more than just “your child will be smarter if they are bilingual.” In addition, they must hear, “your child will be a better person if they are bilingual,” for that is a research-backed conclusion as well. In 2015, a critical study from the University of Chicago suggested that knowledge of foreign languages “foster[s] greater empathy in children⁴⁴.” In this study, Fan et. al describe a complex process in which they isolate the cognitive advantages of multilingualism from its social advantages, finding that children who are exposed to multiple languages gain interpersonal benefits independent of their intellectual development⁴⁵. As they state, “communicative advantages demonstrated by the bilinguals may be social in origin, and not due to enhanced executive control⁴⁶.” The selling point of bilingualism as a means of promoting empathy can be extremely persuasive to parents. In fact, a 2014 Pew Research Center poll found that 69 percent of parents believed that “empathy for others” was one

⁴⁴ Chibber, Kabir. “How Foreign Languages Foster Greater Empathy in Children.” *The Atlantic*, 3 Aug. 2015, <https://www.theatlantic.com/politics/archive/2015/08/how-foreign-languages-foster-greater-empathy-in-children/432462/>.

⁴⁵ Fan et. al. “The Exposure Advantage: Early Exposure to a Multilingual Environment Promotes Effective Communication.” *Psychological Science*, vol. 26(7), 2015, pp. 1090-1097.

⁴⁶ *Ibid.*

of the most important values they wanted to instill in their children⁴⁷. With approximately 12 percent even claiming that it was the single most important value their child can learn⁴⁸.

Ultimately, it is well-established in academia that multilingualism is beneficial to the social, emotional, and intellectual development of children. What is described above represents only the start of research into the most effective ways to communicate these conclusions to a broadly misinformed general public. A tremendous amount of research is necessary in this area. Bilingual education, indeed, is far from the first controversial issue that featured an overwhelming academic consensus that had been ineffective in communicating the evidence it had discovered. Here, perhaps the best parallel to draw is the American public's continual struggle to accept the voracity of the theory of evolution. By the mid-20th century, there was little doubt among any biological scientist that human beings and all other living things evolved over time. Nevertheless, only about 65 percent of Americans accept that assertion, with a stubborn 31 percent adhering to the belief that humans have always "existed in their present form since the beginning"⁴⁹. Most relevant to the issue of multilingualism, however, is the additional fact that despite the best efforts of scientific advocates, this 31 percent has not diminished for decades and shows no signs of doing so⁵⁰. Perhaps, like evolution, perceptions of multilingualism are stuck in an endless purgatory of misinformation. What took centuries to establish in the American consciousness may, fittingly, take centuries to unravel.

⁴⁷"And the Quality Most Parents Want to Teach Their Children Is..." *TIME*, 18 Sep. 2014, <https://time.com/3393652/pew-research-parenting-american-trends/>.

⁴⁸ *Ibid*

⁴⁹ "Chapter 4: Evolution and Perceptions of Scientific Consensus." *Pew Research Center*, 1 July 2015, <https://www.pewresearch.org/science/2015/07/01/chapter-4-evolution-and-perceptions-of-scientific-consensus/>.

⁵⁰ *Ibid*.

CONCLUSION: OUT OF ONE, MANY

There are certainly tactics to portray American monolingualism as an easier problem to tackle than this study did. Indeed, bilingual programs have rooted themselves as a permanent fixture of the American education system, the United States is due for a swing in the progressive direction in regards to immigration and language, and try as they might, organizations like U.S. English have never succeeded in lobbying Congress to pass an English Language Amendment. In light of a thorough review of the past and present states of American attitudes toward language from a historical, social, political, educational and psychological perspective, the reason for pessimism is not based on the belief that reform cannot happen. On the contrary, there has been a demonstrably successful blueprint for reform since the mid-20th century. Instead, the pessimistic orientation of this study centers around the general tendency of linguistic reforms to be reversed amidst the next wave of nativism. The regular about-face that the American public and government performs in regards to language attitudes and policy make improvements in this area feel temporary.

Perhaps the Bilingual Education Act thrived for 30 years, but it was always doomed to end-- if not by the Bush administration in 2001, then likely by the next conservative governing coalition a decade later. Perhaps *Lau v. Nichols* established a historic degree of constitutional protection for bilingual rights, but political will was never sufficient to bear the financial burden of implementing these protections. Perhaps dual immersion schools can slowly promote a greater acceptance of multilingualism and multiculturalism, but the true expansion of these schools would require an eradication of misconceptions regarding bilingualism that have never shown signs of diminishing across the American public. The prognosis for promoting a culture of

American multilingualism appears to be, at its very best, a grim acceptance of a decades-long path to reform.

In the meantime, this study demonstrates that academic literature would be wise to adjust its focus away from intricate case studies into the success of dual immersion programs and into policy-based studies of how to alter public opinion and win congressional favor. Scholars have done an exhaustive job of documenting the benefits of bilingual education and the history of its development. There is no question about the value and necessity of high-quality bilingual programs. What academia lacks, however, is sufficient research into practical methods for implementing these programs. Can support for reform ever be won at the federal level? How does bilingual education separate itself from issues of identity politics and insulate itself from the next wave of anti-immigrant sentiment? What measures can be enacted to promote the cost-effective spread of bilingual course materials to students in underfunded schools? It is these types of questions-- questions surrounding practical steps forward-- that scholars must adopt with a sense of urgency if multilingualism is ever to take root in the United States.

Throughout its history, the United States has relied on the unwavering belief in creating a whole that is greater than the sum of its diverse, abundant parts. In this way, *E pluribus unum* has been more than an American description, it has been an American commitment. Nevertheless, a culture of unity is rarely beneficial when it comes at the expense of a culture of uniqueness. The American solution to its 350 languages has been to emphasize its most prevalent language: just like the United States is one nation out of many states and peoples, English is one language out of many. But from a broad perspective, the philosophy of *E pluribus unum* has only been successful because it works in the other direction as well. Out of one nation, there are many rich cultures, storied histories, beloved traditions, and, yes, beautiful languages that compose it. At its

best, America has embraced this diversity and through its mutual respect of differences established a sense of unity. More than anything else, it is that mutual respect that must develop to alter the American culture of monolingualism. Through the one language that dominates the United States, the growth of many must be encouraged. Of course, such a vague and attractive concept takes massive, multifaceted cultural shifts to attain. America's language problem is here to stay. And out of one problem, many challenges result.